

Emergency of Betawi House Incondet East Jakarta

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Abstract:- The Betawi tribe is a tribe that belongs to the newcomers in Jakarta. This ethnic group was born from a combination of other ethnic groups. In the previous era there has been a mixture of cultural elements that have the forerunner of Betawi culture. This type of research uses the diachronic method which in this study looks at the process of change per period of time. The data collection used is by interview, field survey and literature review. The results showed that there was a non-development land conversion, non-development land use change, the addition of a new road network, morphological changes, and so on.

Keywords: Architecture, Betawi, Betawi House.

I. INTRODUCTION

History has proven that the architecture of the archipelago has always been open to foreign cultural influences, such as the Betawi tribe itself, which is actually a newcomer to Jakarta. The Jakarta area continues to experience urbanization with a fairly high density level. The city of Jakarta also has a fairly high population density. Kampung Condet itself is an area in the city of Jakarta.

Kampung Condet itself used to be cool and full of fruits. Now it has turned into a dense settlement. Condet which initially also gave the image of Betawi has now undergone many changes, both from the physical to the socio-cultural. Acculturation is very influential on architecture. The existence of acculturation in the Condet area is very influential on the process of forming the architecture.

This study aims to determine the influence of immigrants on Betawi culture in the Condet area in shaping architecture and to find out the factors that cause Betawi changes in the Condet area in shaping the architecture of residences and settlements.

II. METHOD

The method used in this study is the diachronic method, namely observing the process of change per period. The research steps consist of; problem formulation, data collection stage, library research, identification and study of data, findings and discussion, and conclusions and suggestions.

Data collection methods are interviews, field surveys, documentation and literature studies. Data analysis used with *synchronous analysis* with issue analysis and diachronic analysis with historical reading.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kampung Condet has been used as a cultural heritage area which in essence has undergone changes. In the past, the condet village felt spacious, comfortable, but now it is no longer. This is due to a change in morphology. In the past, every house must have a 1-2 ha alhan, and now that's no longer the case.

The results of the analysis carried out showed that there had been social and cultural changes in the community. Currently, people seem to not care that the village of Condet has been designated as a cultural heritage. As time goes on, Betawi culture is disappearing like being swallowed by the earth.

Then, the tradition of living in Betawi khawas in Kampung Condet where in one house there are more than one house with a very wide yard, it can also be said that everything has been lost and cannot be found again, this tradition has also undergone changes. Ranging from natives to immigrants. Settlement, trade, industrial services, worship, education and public and social services are divided into five built-up areas on land use in Kampung Condet. The four non-built areas are green open space, RTNH, cemetery, and water recreation green open space. This land use can be interpreted as having mixed functions. From 2004 – 2016 has a core area that continues to grow and follows the direction of the road network to form a linear pattern.

In the last 12 years, land use has changed, which is very visible, namely green open space, river protection which has become a residential area. Overall, the grouping of land development in Kampung Condet is still the same, but there are changes in the function of buildings in the Kampung Condet area. In which there are shops, land for trade, services, and industry. This happened on Jalan Raya Condet and Jalan Batu Ampar. In addition, the physical changes that occur are not increasing the area of the road or widening the dimensions of the road, but repairing roads and road pavements. This is because the land area in Kampung Condet is already quite dense, so it is difficult to expand or widen the road.

The primary system used as a liaison between the regions is Jalan Raya Condet and the secondary system, namely local roads in the area. The addition of a new road network in residential areas can result in spatial interaction so that new links can appear in the area, so that access will increase and the direction of the area can not only be on the main road but also begin to develop on Jalan Batu Ampar. The road network pattern formed in 2004 – 2016 is spinal, radial, and linear.

The buildings in the residential area of Kampung Condet have a mixed pattern, because there is a homogeneous pattern in the residential area. There are also heterogeneous and dispersed ones that can be found in residential areas and service trades. The difference lies in the dominance of the

existing building pattern. In 2004, Kampung Condet was dominated by heterogeneous patterns, this is because the residential area has more than two patterns contained in the building pattern. In 2016 Kampung Condet was dominated by dispersed because it has a pattern that is starting to vary and the density of buildings is also diverse. This is clearly due to the development of built-up land in the Kampung Condet area.

Changes in the building occur in the architectural type of the building which is typical of Betawi culture. This is evidenced by the fact that there are two buildings that still have Betawi architecture. One of the buildings is a place of the area. This is called the gathering place for the Betawi Islamic tradition and the place for the Condet cultural festival celebration which is crowded with local residents and residents at the Condet Village.

The results of the analysis carried out on the land use of the road network, and buildings, it can be seen that the morphology of Kampung Condet has changed, from a beaded linear form in 2004 to an octopus in 2010. This change shows that in 2004 the development of the Kampung Condet area was only centered on the main road. high accessibility and development of area expansion to the side of the area is hampered. Meanwhile, in 2016 the direction of development was not only concentrated on the main road, but also expanded to the side of several dominant roads and continued to develop because there were no significant physical obstacles.

The existence of this Cultural Heritage in the Condet Area includes three sub-districts that are difficult to maintain, and what can be expected is a small part of the Balekambang District, precisely along the Ciliwung River Basin. The Condet cultural heritage area physically can be said to be lost, but socio-culturally it still exists because there are still communities and traditional activities that are carried out routinely.

IV. APPENDIX

Video screenshot	Title
	Settlement Patterns Now and then
	Betawi Condet House Now
	Betawi Condet House Now
	Pictures of buildings in open space

Condet Flat Road Mapping Images

Pictures of South Side Residential Settlements

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that there is a conversion of non-built land into built-up land, changes in non-built land use into built-up land have a percentage of 36.87%, while land use in Condet village in 2004 and 2016 forms a linear pattern and follows the road network.

The addition of a new road network can lead to new social interactions that can create new links in the area, so that access is increasing and the direction of regional relations is not only on the main road. The road patterns that were formed both in 2004 and 106 patterns were formed, namely spinal, linear, and radial.

In 2004 the building pattern in Kampung Condet was dominated by heterogeneous poles with medium building density and in 2016 the building density was high and the building pattern was clearly visible, namely heterogeneous and dispersed patterns. In addition, there are also two buildings with typical Betawi architectural types, which are regional places, which are the pre-group places for Islamic Betawi traditions and the Betawi festival celebrations.

There was a change in morphology from a linear beaded ditanu in 2004 to an octopus in 2016. The change in shape shows that the direction of development is not only centered on the main road in the area but has also expanded to the side of the area following the dominant road network. Existing changes can indicate that the Cultural Conservation area in Kampung Condet is physically lost, but socio-culturally, it still exists because there are still communities and traditional Betawi activities are still often carried out.

Suggestions for the government are that the development that occurs in Condet must be controlled and must think about green open spaces and public spaces which are currently decreasing in existence. In addition, the community must work together to preserve the environment in the Condet area by keeping the Ciliwung River clean, planting trees, and reducing air pollution. This will create an environmental balance in the Condet area.

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